

ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN AUTOMOTIVE WELDING SHOP

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In modern manufacturing practice, energy consumption is getting more and more concern by automotive car manufacturers due to the constantly increasing energy cost and to the ecological burden related to the energy production and use. The great use of electrical energy for industrial operations is responsible for significant CO₂ emissions and thus, climatic changes. According to the data from Tenaga National annual report 2014, 53.8% of the electricity generation is met by natural gas, 35.3% is met by coal, 10.3% by hydropower and 0.6% by distillates [1]. Therefore, higher the energy requirement for manufacturing processes, higher the electrical energy generation required. Hence, higher CO₂ emission rate since most of electricity generation are met by natural gas & coal.

Figure 1

In this study, the actual energy consumption data for 3 months are given by Plant Facilities, and then to be compared with established formula / calculation to predict each single equipment energy consumption at welding shop. Then, this calculation can be used to evaluate future welding shop energy consumption for upcoming project. Moreover, by evaluating every single equipment or tool, the highest energy consumption equipment can be identified and further improvement can be made. This is very important so that new welding shop will be energy efficient and low cost in operation.

In order to develop energy calculation, a series of assumptions are taken into consideration. The two main factors for modelling and calculations are assumed to be the energy (in operation & idle state) and time (in operation & idle state). The following table will elaborate more on the basic assumptions.

	IN OPERATION (PEAK)	IDLE STATE
ENERGY	Equipment move at 100% capacity	Equipment in standby mode
TIME	Working hours / shift	Idle hours

Table 1

For example, to estimate industrial robot energy consumption, 3 states of rated power are taken into account as shown in figure 2 [2];

	Max Rating, kVA	Rated Power, kW		
		Playback (Robot Moving)	Servo On (Robot Standby)	Servo Off (Power for Control)
Industrial Robot	7.7	2.7	0.71	0.16

Figure 2

Then, the rated power to be multiplied with operation time (hours) to estimate the energy consumed by an industrial robot.

The estimation of energy consumption in welding shop based on the following parameters in table 2;

Plant Size	220m x 100m	Automation Level	82%
Line Speed	32 Unit per Hour	Total Stations	185 stations
Total Robot	105 unit	Operation	1 shift

Table 2

Based on 3 months data monitoring, the actual energy consumption reading is then to be compared with calculation based simulation. The comparison can be seen on the figure 3. The down trend of energy consumption is due to reduction of working days in a month.

Figure 3

In average, the different between actual reading and calculation is about 1 %. Since the actual reading is almost the same as calculation, the established formula can be used to simulate energy consumption for each single equipment in welding shop.

The following figure (figure 4) shows the simulation of energy consumption in welding shop. The equipment & electrical appliances are divided into 3 main categories which are main equipment, auxiliary and welding processes.

Figure 4

Based on simulation, the highest energy consumption is from air compressor unit. The compressed air are used in several applications or equipment such as welding jigs (pneumatic cylinder), pneumatic welding guns, hoist, tightening tools and sealant pump. The second highest energy consumption equipment is cooling water unit. This unit is used to circulate water through piping as cooling system in spot welding gun. Surprisingly, energy consumption by welding process is relatively small compared to other equipment. Meaning to say that the process itself is energy efficient enough and even its consumables price (electrode tip, holder) higher than energy it consumed.

In order to design energy efficient factory especially in welding shop, energy efficient equipment need to be considered. For example, using DC with servo controlled welding equipment instead of AC welding equipment may save energy up to 10% as shown in figure 5. Same goes to tightening tools, using electrical tools instead of air tools may save energy up to 38% as shown in figure 6. In general, using electric tool / equipment is more energy efficient compared to air tool / equipment. This strategy is effective in order to reduce compressed air usage in factory.

Figure 5

Figure 6

In term of welding process, even though the energy consumption is relatively small, there is still room for improvement especially during welding parameters setting. Optimized welding parameters may greatly improve the welding quality while reducing energy consumption. For example, by using spot welding process window simulator [3], the energy consumption can be estimated base on parameters setting as shown on figure 7.

Figure 7

In summary, selection of energy efficient equipment and tools are important especially during production line design stage. Operational cost including power and utilities need to be evaluated since in design stage in order to achieve operational excellent in all manufacturing aspects.

References

- [1] ["Tenaga Nasional Annual Report 2014" \(PDF\)](#). Tenaga Nasional. Retrieved 3 November 2016.
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- [3] <https://www.innovationinfo.org/articles/SJASR/SJASR-1-239.pdf>